

ESTIMATION OF CAROTENE IN GREEN VEGETABLES BY THE HILGER-SECTOR PHOTOMETER.

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Carotene content of some thirteen varieties of green vegetables has been determined by the sector-photometric method. Pure β -carotene was taken as the standard. The extraction was done according to a method more or less similar to the procedure followed by Smith, by Schertz and by Wilson, Das-Gupta and Ahmad.

Various methods of colorimetrically estimating carotene in organic solvents are in use. Pyke (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1936, **55**, 1397) has matched the colour in the Loviband tintometer. Guilbert (*Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1934, **6**, 452) has matched the yellow colour against the colour of a mixture of naphthol yellow and orange-G. Attempts have been made to match the colour with solutions of bixin or with solutions of inorganic salts. All these methods, however, suffer from one great drawback, the range of accurate comparison being limited within a comparatively narrow limit of concentration. There is also the additional difficulty of the matching of the exact shade of colour when different comparison standards are used. Most of the above mentioned disadvantages are absent from the spectroscopic method which was employed by Gillam (*Biochem. J.*, 1935, **29**, 1831) and De (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1935, **23**, 505).

The sector-photometric method was, therefore, adopted for the determination of carotene. Light from a condensed spark between two chromium electrodes (in preference to tungsten-steel electrodes as they furnish more lines in the region 4800-5000 $\text{\AA}$) passes through the solvent and the solution of a suitable concentration contained in two tubes of the same length. The emergent beam from the solvent is made to vary in intensity by varying the aperture of the rotating sector, whereas the light after absorption in the material under test passes through another rotating sector of a fixed aperture. A series of photographs is taken on a single photographic plate with the variable sector set to different apertures. Each of these photographs consists of a pair of spectrum photographs in close juxtaposition, one of which is of reduced density throughout its whole length, the other (which passed through the material) being more dense than the first in certain parts and less so in others, there being certain wave-lengths where the densities of the two are equal. The places of equal density being spotted, the absorption curve for a particular concentration of the substance in that solution is obtained. One such curve is given in Fig. 1. For

avoiding any deterioration of carotene in petroleum ether by ultraviolet rays, a solution of quinine sulphate was used as a filter and placed immediately after the source.

For measuring an unknown concentration from its absorption curve, the following procedure was adopted.

The absorption curves for a number of suitable concentrations (0.0015 mg., 0.0020 mg., 0.0025 mg., per c. c.) have been obtained. The intensity of absorption for any wave-length, *viz.*, 4900Å is measured instead of measuring the maximum absorption at 4800Å and 4600Å. The advantage of this method is that it avoids the finding out of the actual concentrations for which the maximum absorption is predominant. Next step is to plot another curve—the intensity of absorption or in other words $\log I_0/I$ (the density readings on the variable sector) for 4900Å along the ordinate and the corresponding concentration along the abscissa, a straight line passing through the origin is obtained. This is called the standard curve (Fig. 2). For measuring an unknown concentration from a knowledge of its absorption at 4900Å, the corresponding reading for the concentration is read from the standard curve.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Methods of Complete Isolation and Purification of Carotene.—The washed green materials were cut into thin slices and dried on trays according

to the method of Schertz (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1938, 30, 1073) at 45-50°. As soon as the leaves became dry enough to crumble easily, they were ground and sieved through a 60 mesh screen of non-corrosive metal containing no copper. The powder was immediately used for extraction.

The powder (2.5 g.) was steeped in 200 c.c. of petroleum ether (b.p. 40°-70°) for 24 hours according to Smith (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1932, 96, 35). The extract was filtered under reduced pressure and the residue was washed several times with petroleum ether until the washings were colourless.

The residue was again washed repeatedly with 85% acetone (Holmes and Leicester, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 54, 716) until the extracts became completely colourless. The combined extracts containing carotene, xanthophyll and chlorophyll were transferred to a separating funnel. Acetone was washed away by shaking repeatedly with distilled water. The ethereal solution was saponified with 29% alcoholic potash according to the method of Willstätter and Mieg (*Ann. Chem.*, 1907, 12, 355) modified by Smith (*loc. cit.*). The contents were kept for 12 hours with occasional stirring. Chlorophyllines were removed by washing with water. In case the solution is not perfectly free from green colouration, saponification was repeated (Wilson, Das-Gupta and Ahmad, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1937, 24, 807). Carotene was isolated from xanthophyll by shaking with 85% methyl alcohol in accordance with the method of Willstätter and Stoll modified by Schertz (*loc. cit.*). The petroleum ether solution was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated to a reduced volume by distillation in vacuum. The solution was now ready for spectroscopic examination after suitable dilution. In case immediate examination was not possible, traces of extra pure hydroquinone were added to the solution and kept in an airtight bottle wrapped in black paper and preserved in a refrigerator.

It might be mentioned here that De (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1936, 23, 937) also determined the carotene content of various vegetables and fruits using a spectrograph coupled with a sector but he followed a different procedure. He determined the extinction coefficient of carotene at 4630Å in petroleum ether or carbon disulphide before and after irradiation in a strong beam of ultraviolet light. Some of the numerical values obtained by him have been given in the accompanying table together with the values of the present author and those obtained by Ahmad and co-workers (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1937, 24, 801) who followed a tintometric method; though the agreement is not exact still the discrepancies become obvious when it is considered.

that carotene content depends on the nature of soil, season, climatic condition etc.

TABLE I.

Carotene content.

Vegetables.	Total carotene in (0.001 mg.) per 100 g. material.		
	Rai-Sircar.	De.	Wilson and co-workers.
Halancha (<i>Enhydra fluctuans</i>)	2666		
Radish leaves (<i>Raphanus sativus</i>).	6666		7200-8600
Lal data (<i>Amaranthus gangeticus</i>).	2000	2520	
Lal sāk (<i>Amaranthus bhītum</i>)	6875		6750
Red puin (<i>Basella rubra</i>).	2100		3200-6500
Kalmi sāk (<i>Ipomoea reptans</i>)	3600		5200-5500
Pumpkin leaves (<i>Cucurbita Pepo</i>)	6250		5750-7200
Betel leaves (<i>Piper betel</i>) (very young).	700		
Do (mature).	8000	7200	12000
Lettuce (<i>Lactuca sativa</i>).	2116	2060	1500-1940
Palang sāk (<i>Beta vulgaris</i>)	2935	2630	
Cabbage (<i>Brassica oleracea</i>) (Inner white leaves).	833	900	
Do (outer green leaves).	2500	2380	
Carrot (<i>Daucus carota</i>)	2082	2000	2000-5600
Coriander (<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>).	13833	12630	
Dheki sāk (<i>Diplazium esculentum</i>).	3450		

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